

CHARACTERISTICS OF HEROIC POEMS: NATIONAL SPIRIT AND TRADITIONS

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Abstract: The article discusses that heroic epics are the source of national education leading to the maturity of generations, not only expressing the life, struggle and dreams of people, but also a means of education leading to the maturity of generations.

Keywords: epic, epic, bakhshi, alpomish, rite, ritual folklore, plot, poetic structure, tradition, educational process, Uzbek folk epic, intangible cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

Epics of national heroism in each line express our national ideology, national ideas and national values, the ideal dream of the people to live happily. conducted. Without cultivating love and respect for one's own people, its traditions, language and culture, it is impossible to bring up a real person who perceives his people as one of the equal in the world community of nations, a lover of his homeland. So, in order to develop a real person who is passionate about his homeland, we must study centuries-old national traditions and inculcate national and universal ideas and values in the minds of today's generation. This, in turn, requires reference to the folklore, in particular, the epic, which is the largest epic genre.

Each nation has its own legendary heroes, heroes it loves and respects. From ancient times, our people have been striving to be worthy of the divine power in their bodies and roots, and have brought up their sons in the spirit of courage, honesty and bravery, as true heroes who will not spare their lives for the country. In this sense, the epic "Alpomish", a unique masterpiece of folklore, is a heroic song that reflects the identity of our nation, passed down from generation to generation. If the ancient and glorious history of our people is an endless epic, then Alpomish is the epitome of this epic.

To understand a nation, one must know its psyche. Alpomish is an incomparable artistic monument in terms of expressing the Uzbek spiritual world in the epic. This is because the Uzbek way of thinking, the way of influencing, the way of making decisions are very sensitive in the play. Many folklorists explain that the themes of the creation of a centralized state, the unification of a divided country, and love provide the development of the Alpomish epic. In our view, at the heart of the epic is ignorance,

ignorance and its impact on human destiny. The work is not meant to contribute to the story, but because the story itself is large-scale, large-scale, and influential. Alpomish's epic describes the characteristics of our people and explains them to students in comparison with other examples of folklore. One of the characteristics of our people is to share their joy with others. In order to increase the interest of students in the epic Alpomish, the teacher should mention how important the epic is in the history of our people. As the tribes, clans, and peoples of the world are formed as separate peoples in history, this process finds its artistic expression, first of all, in a special large, epic play, which is considered a heroic epic. Professor Bahodir Sarimsakov describes the role of the Uzbek epic in the unification of the Uzbek people as an independent people. recognized as an epic. Indeed, the text of the epic contains many signs of past lives, and as a result of their interpretation, we are fully convinced that the work is a folk heroic epic. Indeed, the text of the epic contains many signs of past lives, and as a result of their interpretation, we are fully convinced that the work is a folk heroic epic. The fact is that in the distant past, the independence and inviolability of a country was measured by the wealth of any country that depended on it. In folk tales and epics, it is not appropriate to confuse a particular policy of aggression with the fact that the protagonist's journey to a country is associated with his desire to own that country.

METHODS:

It is worth noting that there is a strong desire to ensure the independence of their country. Therefore, the creators of "Alpomish" deliberately exaggerate the stubbornness of Boysari, justifying his stay in Kalmykia. In fact, Boysari's stay in another country justifies Alpomish's second trip. Interestingly, Alpomish could not directly invade the country of the Kalmyk king Toychikhan. He punishes Toychikhan for the atrocities committed against Boysari and the betrayal committed against him. Alpomish's approach shows that the Uzbek young man is not hesitant to do justice and is ready for any danger. Meanwhile, Alpomish makes his man king of the Kalmyk (Kashal) land. At the same time, it is as if he was fighting for the independence of his country. One can admire the skill of finding such a seemingly invisible solution to every event of our wise people. Alpomish's return to his homeland and ending the injustice in Kungrad-Boysun can be seen as a natural conclusion. Although many scenes in the epic "Alpomish" seem insignificant at first glance, the teacher should emphasize that the people through them expressed their life experiences and explain them with examples. . For example, a letter from Barchinoy to Alpomish is blocked by Boybori. This shows that Boybori refused to follow the path he had begun, that is, to marry Barchinga's son and return Boysun to his homeland. As the story unfolds, the Swallow begins to play a decisive role. He accidentally finds Barchin's letter in a box and sends his brother on a journey to bring his bride. Such a trip is considered one of the main features of the folk heroic epic. When Alpomish arrives in the land of the

Kalmyks, he becomes one of the fulfillment of Barchin's condition of ninety alpes. For example, his Boychibor horse joins the four hundred and ninety-nine horses in the race and becomes the five hundredth tulpar to compete in the race that began for Barchin. In this way, the people show that Alpomish is the strongest, the sniper, the best. So after his horse wins the race, he proves himself by taking part in archery, coin toss, and ninety alpine wrestling. This test also corresponds to the characteristics of a heroic epic. The events surrounding Barchinoy in the epic are described with special affection by the bakhshis. He is not inferior to Alpomish in terms of intelligence and entrepreneurship. When Surkhail's sons tried to force Barchinoy to marry her, the girl picked up one of the alpins and hit the ground so that foam splashed from the wrestler's mouth. Only then will the Alps have to give Barchinoy six months to wait for Alpomish.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

To sum up, the epic "Alpomish" is a favorite epic of our people, which embodies nostalgia, love for the motherland, loyalty to friends and family in beautiful paintings. Teacher emphasizes the importance of "Alpomish" among the Uzbek folk epics, as it embodies many of the qualities of our people, and it is expedient to list them one by one, the peculiarities of the Uzbek people: motherland the love that exists, the boundless devotion to the country; hospitality and hospitality; generosity and honesty; respect and esteem for the elderly; respect for women; feelings of loyalty to friends and family; the appreciation of feelings such as love and friendship. In the process of passing the epic, teacher should pay special attention to these aspects of the work, paying special attention to the educational aspect of the work. After all, heroic epics testify to the existence of unique national spirit and traditions, high culture, beautiful traditions, immortal values, unique ceremonies, and still live for centuries.

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